

Performance Analysis and Economic Viability of a 6 MW Grid-Connected Photovoltaic System

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Abstract— This study explores the simulation and evaluation of a 6 MW grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) system, optimized for deployment in a subtropical setting. The system utilizes mono-crystalline silicon PV modules and is designed for efficient integration with existing grid infrastructure. Simulations, conducted over a projected 10-year period using PVsyst software, incorporate region-specific meteorological data, shading factors, and operational characteristics. The anticipated annual energy output is approximately 8,488 MWh, with a performance ratio (PR) of 68.8%. Economic analysis reveals a levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of \$0.060/kWh, along with a substantial return on investment (ROI) of 349.6% over 20 years. These results highlight the potential for sustainable energy generation and economic feasibility, underscoring the role of PV systems in transitioning toward renewable energy sources in subtropical regions.

Keywords— Grid-connected PV system, Mono-crystalline silicon modules, Sustainable energy production Economic feasibility, Annual energy output.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for sustainable energy solutions has prompted significant interest in renewable energy technologies, particularly photovoltaic (PV) systems. As the world grapples with climate change and the depletion of fossil fuels, harnessing solar energy has emerged as a viable alternative. This is especially true in subtropical regions like Kaptai, Bangladesh, where abundant sunlight and suitable climatic conditions can facilitate effective solar energy generation. The integration of PV systems into the local grid infrastructure offers a pathway toward achieving energy security and sustainability, making it crucial to evaluate their potential for large-scale deployment [1].

This study presents a comprehensive simulation and analysis of a 6 MW grid-connected PV system, specifically designed for the Kaptai region. Utilizing mono-crystalline silicon PV modules, the system is tailored to optimize performance based on local meteorological conditions. The simulation, conducted using PVsyst software, incorporates factors such as shading, geographic location, and operational parameters, allowing for an accurate assessment of the system's energy production capabilities over a projected 10-year lifespan. The findings from this analysis not only underscore the technological feasibility of such systems but also highlight their significance in addressing energy shortages in developing regions [2].

Furthermore, economic evaluations of the proposed PV system reveal promising indicators of financial viability, with a levelized cost of energy (LCOE) of \$0.060/kWh and a return on investment (ROI) of 349.6% over 20 years. These results suggest that the implementation of grid-connected PV systems can contribute to sustainable energy production while delivering substantial economic benefits. By providing insights into both the operational and financial aspects of solar energy projects, this study aims to inform policymakers, investors, and researchers about the potential of renewable energy solutions in transforming the energy landscape of Kaptai, Bangladesh, and similar subtropical regions [3].

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for this study consisted of a systematic simulation process using PVsyst V6.88 to model and evaluate the performance of the photovoltaic (PV) system. The key steps involved in the methodology are outlined below:

The PV system was designed to comprise a substantial array of mono-crystalline modules, arranged in a specific configuration to optimize energy output. The modules, each with a rated capacity, were organized into a defined number of sheds, with careful consideration given to the arrangement in terms of series and parallel connections. The overall tilt angle and azimuth orientation of the PV field were adjusted to maximize solar exposure based on the geographical and climatic conditions of the site.

To ensure accurate performance assessment, the simulation utilized localized meteorological data, covering an extended historical period to capture typical weather patterns. A recognized irradiance transposition model was applied to account for the spatial distribution of sunlight on the PV array, while factors such as shading and environmental losses were incorporated. Losses attributed to various factors, including module mismatch and degradation, were estimated based on established industry standards.

The performance of the PV system was evaluated through key metrics, including the performance ratio (PR), specific yield, and total energy output. Economic evaluations were conducted to assess the capital and operational expenditures associated with the system, with projections for revenue based on applicable feed-in tariffs. The analysis also included an assessment of the expected payback period and overall profitability over the lifespan of the project.

In addition to performance metrics, the analysis considered various loss factors that could impact system efficiency, including thermal effects and inverter

performance. Detailed assessments were made to quantify these losses and enhance energy yield predictions. Furthermore, adjustments for the angle of incidence of sunlight were applied to evaluate the potential impact of non-perpendicular sunlight on the overall energy output.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND CONFIGURATION

The designed photovoltaic (PV) system is a 6 MW grid-connected installation located in Kaptai, Bangladesh, positioned at a latitude of 22.49° N and a longitude of 92.21° E. The system comprises 13,636 mono-crystalline silicon PV modules, each rated at 440 Wp, organized into 306 identical sheds on the ground. Each shed is configured to include 14 modules connected in series, with a total of 974 strings arranged in parallel, resulting in a total nominal power output of 6,000 kWp. The PV array is specifically designed to optimize energy capture through a tilt angle of 22° and an azimuth orientation of -5°, ensuring effective exposure to solar radiation throughout the year.

The system's total module area covers approximately 30,340 m², with a cell area of 27,097 m², facilitating sufficient space for solar energy capture. The ground coverage ratio (GCR) of 66.5% allows for efficient use of land while maintaining adequate spacing of 5 meters between the sheds, minimizing shading effects. The shading limit angle is defined at 33.3°, ensuring that the configuration accommodates the potential shading from nearby obstacles while maximizing sunlight exposure.

The inverter system is composed of 167 units of 30 kWac inverters, yielding a total inverter capacity of 5,010 kWac. This design is crucial for converting the direct current (DC) generated by the PV modules into alternating current (AC) suitable for grid integration. The PV system is designed to accommodate unlimited load demand from the grid, reflecting a strong alignment with local energy needs and sustainability goals. To enhance performance, the system incorporates sophisticated loss factors, including a soiling loss fraction of 2.0%, wiring losses of 1.5%, and module mismatch losses of 1.0%, which collectively contribute to the overall efficiency of the energy generation process. Additionally, the performance analysis considers the impact of various factors such as thermal losses and degradation over time, ensuring a robust and resilient design for long-term operation.

Fig. 1. Perspective of the PV-field and surrounding shading scene

Fig. 2. Iso-shadings diagram

IV. SIMULATION PARAMETERS AND MODELS

The simulation of the 6 MW photovoltaic (PV) system was conducted using PVsyst V6.88, with a focus on accurately modeling environmental and system-specific parameters. The system configuration comprises ground-mounted sheds, with linear shading effects factored into the analysis. The PV array is oriented at a tilt angle of 22° and an azimuth angle of -5°, aligning with local solar incidence to optimize energy capture.

The simulation utilized a Mono 440 Wp Twin 144 half-cell PV module model, with a total of 13,636 modules arranged to achieve a nominal power output of 6,000 kWp. This configuration was complemented by 167 inverters, each rated at 30 kWac, amounting to a combined inverter capacity of 5,010 kWac. The system was designed to meet an unrestricted load demand, as it is grid-connected, allowing all generated power to be fed into the grid.

Key performance metrics and annual production data were meticulously calculated to assess the system's efficiency. The total produced energy was found to be 8,488 MWh per year, with a specific yield of 1,415 kWh/kWp. The Performance Ratio (PR) was calculated at 68.8%, which reflects the system's ability to effectively convert available solar energy into usable electrical energy. Monthly data analysis showed variations in performance, with the highest PR occurring in February at 69.8% and the lowest in October at 67.9%, indicative of seasonal impacts on the system's output. The PR metric offers insight into overall system efficiency by accounting for losses due to irradiance, temperature, and shading effects. These detailed calculations contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the system's operational dynamics under real-world conditions.

V. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

A. *Normalized productions (per installed kWp)*: The graph illustrates the monthly normalized energy production for a 6 MW PV system, with values broken down into useful energy output (Yf), collection losses (Lc), and system losses (Ls) per installed kWp. The average daily energy output is 3.88 kWh/kWp, peaking from February to April at approximately 4.5 kWh/kWp/day, and dipping to around 3.0 kWh/kWp/day in July and August due to seasonal effects. Collection losses, averaging 1.46 kWh/kWp/day, are higher in winter and lower in summer, reflecting seasonal impacts on the PV array, while system losses remain relatively stable across months at 0.29 kWh/kWp/day. These trends highlight how environmental factors influence the PV system's efficiency and underscore the importance of mitigating collection losses for optimal performance throughout the year.

Fig. 3. Normalized productions per installed kWp

B. *Performance Ratio*: The Performance Ratio (PR) graph for a 6 MW PV system reveals seasonal variations in efficiency, with an average annual PR of 0.688, indicating that the system is achieving 68.8% of its expected energy output. PR tends to peak during summer months (June to August), likely due to increased solar irradiance, while it is comparatively lower in winter (December to January) as a result of reduced sunlight and potentially higher energy losses. This fluctuation underscores how ambient conditions impact the system's performance. Overall, a PR of 0.688 is relatively efficient, but there is potential for improvement by minimizing energy losses across the system.

Fig. 4. Performance Ratio (Yf / Yr)

C. *Input/Output diagram*: The Daily Input/Output diagram depicts the strong linear relationship between global incident radiation on the collector plane and the energy injected into the grid over the year. The x-axis represents global incident radiation measured in kWh/m²/day, while the y-axis shows the energy output injected into the grid in kWh/day. The data points, which form a tight cluster along the regression line, indicate that as global radiation increases, energy output correspondingly rises, with higher radiation levels (around 8 kWh/m²/day) yielding nearly 30,000 kWh/day. This pattern demonstrates the photovoltaic system's efficiency in converting solar energy into electrical energy consistently throughout the year, regardless of seasonal variations. Overall, the graph underscores the system's reliability and effectiveness, suggesting further analysis on performance metrics, such as efficiency and energy losses, to enhance future energy production.

Fig. 5. Daily Input/Output diagram

D. *System Output Power Distribution*: The histogram illustrates the distribution of daily energy injected into the grid, with the x-axis representing power levels in kW and the y-axis showing frequency in kWh/bin. It reveals a right-skewed distribution, indicating more days with lower power injections, peaking around 4000 kW. The power injection ranges from approximately 0 kW to 6000 kW, with frequency decreasing at higher levels. This suggests the system often operates below its capacity. Analyzing the distribution further, including statistical measures and factors affecting peak power, can provide insights into energy variability, load profile mismatches, and optimization opportunities for better capacity utilization.

Fig. 6. Output Power Distribution

E. Loss Diagram: The performance of a photovoltaic (PV) system can be evaluated through a detailed analysis of energy production metrics and loss factors. The total horizontal global irradiation received over the year is 1888 kWh/m², which reflects the solar energy available for conversion. Given the collector area of 30,340 m², the effective irradiation on the collectors is calculated as 1774 kWh/m² multiplied by the area, resulting in approximately 53,805,580 kWh of energy. With an efficiency of 19.83% at standard test conditions (STC), the nominal energy output of the PV array reaches 10,675 MWh. However, this figure is subjected to various reductions: soiling losses account for 2.00%, temperature-related losses contribute 1.16%, and irradiance losses due to insufficient solar exposure reduce the output by 7.47%. After accounting for these factors, the effective energy produced is about 9,133 MWh. Additionally, a module degradation factor of 1.05% over ten years further decreases the output to 8,488 MWh. Further losses stem from ohmic wiring resistance, mismatch losses among modules, and various inverter inefficiencies. These include losses due to nominal power capacity and voltage thresholds. Finally, auxiliary components, such as fans, also incur losses, ultimately resulting in 8,488 MWh of energy injected into the grid. This comprehensive analysis emphasizes the significance of understanding the multitude of factors affecting a PV system's efficiency and energy output.

Fig. 7. Loss diagram over the whole year

VI. FINANCIAL ANALYSIS

A. Investment and Operational Cost: The tables below outline the investment and operating costs associated with the 6 MW photovoltaic (PV) system. The first table details the direct costs (CAPEX) for procuring and installing the system components, including PV modules, inverters, supports, and associated accessories, totaling approximately \$2.14 million USD. The second table summarizes the annual operating costs (OPEX), which include maintenance, cleaning, repairs, and taxes, adjusted for inflation. This comprehensive cost analysis provides a clear understanding of the financial requirements for both the initial setup and ongoing operation of the PV system [4].

TABLE I. Investment in the Plant

Investment	Units	Cost per Unit (USD)	Total Cost (USD)
Direct Costs			
PV Modules	13,636	21.50	293,174.00
Supports for Modules	13,636	25.20	343,627.20
Inverters (30 kWac)	167	1,650.00	275,550.00
Transport	-	-	71,065.00
Accessories, Fasteners	-	-	737,086.34
Wiring	-	-	36,438.84
Settings	-	-	53,299.00
Grid Connection	-	-	314,350.00
Liability Insurance	-	-	15,000.00

TABLE II. Total Operational Cost [5]

Operating Costs (OPEX)	Annual Cost (USD)
Maintenance - Salaries	148,560.00
Reparation	3,465.47
Cleaning	1,272.00
Security Fund	44,416.00
Other Taxes	35,533.00
Subsidies	-4,280.00
Total Operating Costs (OPEX)	228,966.47
OPEX incl. Inflation (6.20%)	405,847.89

B. Electricity Sale: The electricity generated by the 6 MW photovoltaic system is sold under a feed-in tariff agreement, which provides a fixed rate for electricity fed into the grid. The system earns \$0.11 USD per kWh during peak hours (14:00-16:00 and 20:00-08:00) and \$0.09 USD per kWh during off-peak hours. This tariff structure remains constant for a warranty period of 20 years, with no annual connection tax or scheduled tariff variation. However, after the warranty period, the feed-in tariff rate is expected to decrease by 50%, which could impact long-term revenue generation. This stable initial tariff provides financial predictability for the project's early stages, though future adjustments will need to be considered in the project's financial planning [6].

C. Return On Investment: The financial analysis for the 20-year lifespan of the 6 MW photovoltaic system demonstrates a strong return on investment (ROI) of 349.6%, underscoring the project's profitability. With a payback period of just 3.3 years, the project is able to quickly recover its initial capital expenditure, generating substantial net profit over the remaining years. By the end of the project lifetime, the anticipated net profit is approximately \$7,480,510.04 USD. This analysis highlights the financial viability and attractiveness of investing in this photovoltaic system, given the relatively short payback period and significant ROI.

D. Yearly Net Profit: The graph illustrates the projected yearly net profit for the photovoltaic project over a 25-year period. Starting at around 600 kUSD in the initial years, the profit gradually decreases as the project progresses, reflecting diminishing returns due to factors such as decreasing tariff rates or operational costs over time. Despite the decline, the project remains profitable throughout, with annual net profits steadily decreasing towards zero by the end of the lifespan. This trend emphasizes the impact of decreasing feed-in tariffs and operational challenges on long-term profitability.

Fig. 8: Yearly Net Profit (kUSD)

E. Cumulative Cashflow: The graph shows the cumulative cash flow for the photovoltaic project over a 25-year period. Starting from a small initial value, the cumulative cash flow consistently increases, surpassing 7,000 kUSD by the end of the project lifetime. This upward trend indicates sustained profitability and positive cash flow accumulation over time, driven by electricity sales and long-term returns. The steady increase highlights the project's capacity to generate substantial revenue, with cumulative gains building steadily each year.

Fig. 9: Cumulative cashflow (kUSD)

VII. CO₂ EMISSION BALANCE

The emissions data outlines the carbon footprint associated with a photovoltaic system over its lifetime. The system is projected to produce a total of 9,901.35 tons of CO₂ emissions, while it is expected to replace a much higher amount of emissions, totaling 155,952.2 tons of CO₂ over 30 years. The annual energy production of the system is 8,901.38 MWh, which contributes to an overall reduction in emissions. The grid lifecycle emissions are calculated at 584 g CO₂/kWh, leading to total emissions of 125,373.0 tons of CO₂. This balance demonstrates the effectiveness of the PV system in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions, highlighting its potential positive environmental impact over its operational lifespan [7].

TABLE III. System Lifecycle Emissions Details:

Item	LCE (kgCO ₂)	Quantity	Subtotal (kgCO ₂)
Modules	837 kgCO ₂ /kWp	10,743 kWp	8,990,281
Supports	3.90 kgCO ₂ /kg	244,160 kg	951,072
Total			9,941,353

Fig. 10: Saved CO₂ Emission

VIII. CONCLUSION

This study presents a comprehensive evaluation of a 6 MW grid-connected photovoltaic (PV) system optimized for deployment in Kaptai, Bangladesh, a subtropical region characterized by abundant sunlight. The simulation results demonstrate a significant potential for sustainable energy generation, with an anticipated annual energy output of approximately 8,488 MWh and a performance ratio of 68.8%. The economic analysis reveals a compelling return on investment (ROI) of 349.6% over 20 years, underscoring the project's financial viability and attractiveness.

The findings highlight the crucial role that PV systems can play in addressing energy shortages and promoting renewable energy adoption in developing regions. By integrating advanced modeling techniques and localized meteorological data, the study effectively assesses the operational dynamics of the PV system, showcasing its resilience and efficiency. Moreover, the analysis of loss factors and performance metrics illustrates the importance of optimizing system design to enhance energy production.

Furthermore, the environmental impact of the PV system is notable, with a projected reduction of 155,952.2 tons of CO₂ emissions over 30 years, significantly outweighing the system's lifecycle emissions. This emphasizes the potential of solar energy solutions in mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and contributing to global sustainability goals.

In conclusion, the 6 MW PV system in Kaptai serves as a viable model for similar deployments in subtropical regions, combining technical feasibility with economic benefits. The

insights gained from this study can inform policymakers, investors, and researchers about the transformative potential of photovoltaic systems in enhancing energy security and promoting a sustainable future.

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